

METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF MANAGEMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE TRANSACTION COSTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742966>

Annotatsiya: Uchbu tezisda sanoat korxonalarida biznes xavfini hisoblash va yaxshi ta'minotchini tanlash, shartnoma qiymatini minimallashtirish, yetkazib beruvchini tanlash va bazasini tayyorlash muammolarini yechimi ko'rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so'zi: korxonalar, mahsulot, xavf, omil, xaridor, yetkazib beruvchi, ta'minot, mehnat, mehnat unumdorlig, buyurtma, sotish, ko'rsatkich.

Аннотация: В этих трех тезисах показаны решения задач расчета бизнес-рисков и выбора хорошего поставщика, минимизации стоимости контракта, выбора поставщика и подготовки базы на промышленных предприятиях.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, товар, риск, фактор, покупатель, поставщик, предложение, труд, производительность труда, заказ, реализация, показатель.

Abstract: In these three theses, the solutions to the problems of business risk calculation and selection of a good supplier, minimization of contract value, supplier selection, and base preparation are shown in industrial enterprises.

Keywords: enterprise, product, risk, factor, buyer, supplier, supply, labor, labor productivity, order, sales, indicator.

Enter. Economic-mathematical model of contract value minimization at the stage of searching for suppliers One of the reasons for choosing suppliers instead of own production is the increase in economic efficiency, flexibility, and competence level. The transition from a classic approach to a new approach in supplier relations tends to deeper collaboration and outsourcing, which further increases the reputation of

industrial enterprise suppliers. If a company chooses a weak supplier, it will affect its customers. They begin to see the company as a weak supplier due to poor product quality, and broken delivery times. Therefore, choosing a suitable supplier is a responsible process in modern business.

The main part. A good supplier may not always provide goods and services at the lowest price, the shortest delivery time, or the best technical support, even if the above is considered a competitive advantage in supplier selection. A good supplier can provide high returns and low risk. The main factors of competitiveness in modern business are flexibility and the ability to accept risk. Choosing a supplier means calculating business risk and choosing a good supplier means minimizing business risk [1].

The most natural approach is to choose a supplier based on an analysis of the financial situation. Many companies prefer to work with big players financially. Is this approach correct? A small supplier is more flexible: it is easier for him to control and direct capital flows than a large supplier. The capital flows of large suppliers are usually fixed and stable, but the flow cycle is fragile when faced with problems. In this case, the flexible system of circulation of flows is more important than the total amount of capital [2].

Traditionally, the relationship between the buyer and the supplier is built in such a way that both parties carry the business risk independently. However, this has changed over the past decade. Now the enterprise "looks" not only at the quality of the supplier's production but also at its internal operational processes and management processes. This changes the relationship between the buyer and the supplier. Today, businesses tend to share risks with suppliers to reduce the likelihood of opportunism.

Supplier selection by an industrial enterprise: Supplier selection is the process of evaluating and selecting suppliers for an industrial enterprise's supply chain [3]. The general purpose of supplier selection is as follows:

- reducing supply risk;

- maximizing the total volume of purchases;
- building a close and long-term relationship between the buyer and the supplier.

Usually, a company decides to find a new supplier for the following reasons:

- an unexpected increase in the purchase price;
- the need to maintain the confidentiality of the design;
- lack of technical competence of the suppliers;
- poor service provided by current suppliers;
- unexpected deterioration of the supplier's labor productivity.

A generalized procurement cycle may include the following stages:

- determination of product demand;
- determining the properties of raw materials or materials;
- deciding on production or purchase;
- preparing a database of offers for purchase;
- selection of sources.

The organization should make the following choices: purchase from one supplier or select several suppliers by the goals of the enterprise. Usually, this stage is divided into four parts:

- selection of criteria for evaluating the explicit and implicit characteristics of the selection of suppliers;
- choosing the appropriate method of supplier selection;
- selection of suppliers;
- distribution of the order to selected suppliers using mathematical modeling.

In the scientific literature, the most common criteria for selecting suppliers are as follows. Thus, selecting a supplier includes four stages.

1. Putting the problem.
2. Formation of adjectives.
3. Selection of qualified suppliers.
4. Final selection of suppliers.

The qualities that describe a good supplier vary depending on the company, its product, and its production process. A summarized list of the qualities of the mentioned suppliers can be as follows.

1. Delivery on time.
2. Technical features.
3. The quality is good.
4. The price is reasonably low.
5. Historical data on previous performance.
6. The ability to maintain the necessary level of flexibility to withstand unexpected fluctuations in demand.
7. Pre-sale and after-sale support.
8. The ability to provide customers with the ability to monitor the delivery process. Such a control process can increase the reliability of delivery.
9. Industry certifications such as ISO or TUV.
10. Actively develop healthy relationships with customers.

Preparation of the supplier base: A stable supplier base can improve the availability of raw materials, spare parts, and materials, improve the bargaining power of the industrial enterprise, and increase the ability to establish contact with the best supplier. Preparation of the supplier base Supplier selection is the most discussed topic in the literature, with the main focus on supplier selection and evaluation. The main focus should be on the preparation of the supplier base because a poor base reduces the probability of selecting a good supplier even when a reliable selection method is used.

Summary. There are several criteria for preparing a supplier base:

- suppliers' reputation and industry certification;
- the presence of past indicators of the supplier, the presence of authorized documents;

- availability of a well-documented product catalog (for raw materials, a well-documented test report containing the chemical and physical properties of the supplied raw materials);
- the ability to ensure the delivery of goods within the specified period;
- the technical know-how of the suppliers for the new product should be checked and the equipment of the suppliers should be checked.

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